

Request to participate in medical research:

Tolerability of the COVID-19 vaccine in patients with postural tachycardia syndrome

Dear Madam, Dear Sir

We are asking you here if you would be willing to participate in our research project. Your participation is voluntary. All data collected in this research project is subject to strict data protection regulations.

The research project is being conducted by Prof. Werner Z'Graggen. If you are interested, we will be happy to inform you about the results of this research project.

We will explain the most important points to you and answer your questions. So that you can already get a picture, here are the most important things first. Further, more detailed information will follow.

Why are we carrying out this research project?

- To date, the tolerability and side effects of the COVID-19 vaccine (so-called mRNA vaccines from Moderna and from Pfizer) have not been investigated or described in any study in patients with POTS.
- In this research project, we want to investigate how well these COVID-19 vaccinations are tolerated by patients with POTS and whether there is a persistent increase in POTS symptoms in the course of the vaccinations. In addition, the worsening of POTS symptoms in patients infected with COVID-19 will also be evaluated.

What do I have to do when I participate? - What happens to me when I participate?

- If you decide to take part, this research project will involve a telephone interview of about 30 minutes. The interview is in two parts: In the first part, you will be asked about any side effects you may have had from the COVID-19 vaccinations. In the second part, you will be asked to assess whether your symptoms of POTS have changed after receiving the vaccinations, and if so, for how long. You will be asked the same questions if you have had a COVID-19 disease.

What are the benefits and risks involved?

Benefit

- You will not personally benefit from taking part in this research project. However, the results may be important for other people who have the same disease.

Risk and burden

- There is no specific risk involved in participating in this research project.
- During data collection, the data is encrypted. Encryption means that all reference data that could identify you (name, date of birth) is deleted and replaced by a key.

With your signature at the end of the document, you attest that you are participating voluntarily and that you have understood the contents of the entire document.

Detailed information

1. Aim and selection

We refer to our research project as a *research project* in this handout. If you participate in this research project, you are a *participant*.

In this research project, we primarily want to investigate how well the COVID-19 vaccine (so-called mRNA vaccines from Moderna and Pfizer) is tolerated by patients with postural tachycardia syndrome (POTS) and whether there is a persistent increase in POTS symptoms as a result of the vaccination. We are also investigating whether COVID-19 disease leads to a sustained increase in POTS symptoms. We are asking you to participate because all people who have been diagnosed with POTS and have received vaccinations against COVID-19 or have had a COVID-19 disease can participate.

2. General information

- This is a national research project that will only be carried out at the Inselspital Bern. It is planned to carry out the research project with an expected 25 people. Participation in the research project takes about 30 minutes for you.
- POTS is a disease of the autonomic nervous system in which the pulse increases excessively (by more than 30 beats per minute) in the upright body position in response to increased blood loss to the lower extremities. In addition to the excessive pulse increase, patients are characterised by the occurrence of other symptoms exclusively in the upright position (= orthostatic intolerance).
- In recent years, there has been increasing evidence that the development of the disorder of the autonomic nervous system in a subgroup of POTS patients could be immune-mediated (= "autoimmune", i.e. caused by a faulty reaction of the immune system). For example, it is known that the onset of POTS is usually triggered by immunological stress factors such as viral infections, trauma, pregnancy, or surgery. In addition, viral diseases are known triggers for a persistent exacerbation of POTS symptoms, which typically persists for four to six weeks beyond the resolution of the infection.
- Several cases of new-onset POTS following COVID-19 infection have been described this year. There is also a case report describing the occurrence of POTS as a side effect of the COVID-19 vaccine. However, the data on this is very limited and largely unclear.
- To date, no studies have investigated or described the tolerability and side effects of the COVID-19 vaccine in patients with POTS. We aim to address this research gap by investigating the side effects of the COVID-19 vaccine in patients with POTS and evaluating whether patients experienced worsening of symptoms due to the vaccine. In addition, we will also evaluate the worsening of symptoms in POTS patients who were infected with COVID-19.
- Your standard treatment will not be changed as part of this study.
- We are doing this research project as required by the laws in Switzerland. We also observe all internationally recognised guidelines. The responsible ethics committee has reviewed the research project.

3. Procedure

If you agree to participate, you will be interviewed by telephone for about 30 minutes as part of this research project. The interview is in two parts: In the first part, you will be asked about any side effects you may have had from the COVID-19 vaccines (mRNA vaccines from Moderna and from Pfizer). In the second part, you are asked to assess whether your symptoms of POTS have increased after receiving the vaccines, and if so, for how long. For example: "Did you experience an increase in dizziness after the first (or second) COVID-19 vaccination? For how many days did dizziness increase?" For patients who have had a COVID-19 infection, the same questions from both parts of the interview are asked first about symptoms of the COVID-19 infection itself and then also about the increase in POTS symptoms after the infection.

4. Benefit

You will not personally benefit from participating. However, the results may be important for other people who have the same disease.

5. Voluntariness and obligations

You are participating voluntarily. If you do not want to participate in this research project or later withdraw your participation, you do not have to justify this. Your treatment and care is guaranteed regardless of your decision.

If you are participating in this research project, you are asked to:

- inform your investigator about concurrent treatment and therapy with other doctors and about the intake of medicines (including medicines of complementary and alternative medicine).

6. Risks and burdens

There is no specific risk involved in participating in this research project.

7. Alternatives

If you do not want to take part in this research project but are open to the possibility of taking part in other research projects, please talk to your investigator.

8. Results

Your investigator may send you a summary of the overall results at the end of the research project.

9. Data confidentiality

Your personal and medical data will be collected for this project. Only very few professionals will see your unencrypted data, and only to perform tasks within the project. When data is collected for study purposes, it will be encrypted. Encryption means that all reference data that could identify you (name, date of birth) are deleted and replaced by a key. The key list always remains in the Inselspital. Those persons who do not know the key cannot draw any conclusions about your person. In the event of publication, the summarised data cannot therefore be traced back to you as an individual. Your name never appears on the internet or in a publication. Sometimes there is a requirement in a journal for publication that individual data (so-called raw data) must be submitted. If individual data must be submitted, then the data is always encrypted and therefore also not traceable to you as a person. All persons who have access to your data within the framework of the project are subject to the duty of confidentiality. Data protection regulations are adhered to and you, as a participant, have the right to access your data at any time.

It is possible that your data will be further used for other studies at a later date or will later be sent to and used in another database in Switzerland for studies that have not yet been defined in more detail (further use). This other database must comply with the same standards as the database for this study. For this further use, we ask you to sign another consent form at the very end of this document. This study may be reviewed by the relevant ethics committee or by the institution that initiated the study. The investigator may have to disclose your personal and medical information for such reviews. All persons must maintain absolute confidentiality.

10. Resignation

You can withdraw from the research project at any time. In this case, however, the data and samples collected up to that point will still be evaluated in encrypted form. In the event of withdrawal, your data and samples will remain encrypted in the project documents. This is for your medical safety. Please check whether you agree to this before you participate in the project.

11. Compensation

If you participate in this project, you will not receive any compensation. There are no costs to you or your health insurance company for participating.

12. Liability

This study is an observational study only. No harm can occur as part of the study.

13. Funding

The project is funded by the Department for Neurosurgery, University Hospital Bern. There is no dependence on the companies listed above.

14. Contact person(s)

You may ask questions about project participation at any time. Also, if you have any uncertainties that arise during the research project or afterwards, please contact:

Prof. Dr. med. Werner Z'Graggen
Senior Physician, Departments of Neurosurgery and Neurology, University Hospital Bern
Freiburgstrasse, 3010 Bern
Telephone number: 031 632 79 09

Declaration of consent

Written declaration of consent to participate in a research project

Please read this form carefully. Please ask if there is anything you do not understand or would like to know. Your written consent is required for participation.

BASEC number (after submission):	
Title of the research project (scientific and lay language):	Tolerability of the COVID-19 vaccine in patients with postural tachycardia syndrome
Responsible institution (project management with address):	Inselspital Bern, Freiburgstrasse, 3010 Bern
Place of implementation:	Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Inselspital, Freiburgstrasse, 3010 Bern
Head of the research project at the place of study: Surname and first name in block capitals:	Prof. Dr. med. Werner Z'Graggen
Participant: Surname and first name in block capitals: Date of birth:	

- I have been informed verbally and in writing by the undersigned investigator about the purpose, the procedure of the research project, about possible advantages and disadvantages as well as about possible risks.
- I am voluntarily participating in this research project and accept the content of the written information provided on the above research project. I have had sufficient time to make my decision.
- My questions in connection with participation in this research project have been answered. I will keep the written information and receive a copy of my written informed consent.
- I agree that the responsible experts of the project management and the ethics committee in charge of this research project may inspect my unencrypted data for testing and control purposes, but in strict compliance with confidentiality.
- I will be informed of results that directly affect my health. If I do not wish to be informed, I will inform my investigator.
- I know that my health-related and personal data can only be passed on in encrypted form for research purposes for this research project. The sponsor guarantees that data protection in accordance with Swiss standards will be observed.
- I can withdraw from participation at any time and without giving reasons. My continued treatment is guaranteed regardless of participation in the research project. The data and samples collected up to that point will still be used for the evaluation of the research project.

Declaration of consent for further use of data in encrypted form

BASEC number (after submission):	
Title of the research project (scientific and lay language):	Tolerability of the COVID-19 vaccine in patients with postural tachycardia syndrome
Participant: Surname and first name in block capitals: Date of birth:	

- I give permission for my encrypted data from this research project to be further used for medical research.
- I understand that the samples are encrypted and the key is stored securely. The data and samples can be sent to other databases for analysis in Switzerland and abroad if they comply with the same standards as in Switzerland. All legal requirements for data protection are complied with.
- I decide voluntarily and can withdraw this decision at any time. If I withdraw, my data will be anonymised. I only inform my investigator and do not have to justify this decision.
- Normally, all the data is evaluated as a whole and the results are published in summary form. If there is a result that is important for my health, it is possible that I will be contacted. If I do not wish to be contacted, I will inform my investigator.
- I give permission for my data and samples to be anonymised and understand that in this case I can neither be informed of random results nor withdraw from the research project.
- If results from the data are commercialised, I am not entitled to a share of the commercial use.

Place, date	Signature of the participant

Confirmation by the investigator: I hereby confirm that I have explained to this participant the nature, significance and implications of the further use of data.

Place, date	Surname and first name of the investigator in block capitals
	Signature of the investigator